

carbofuran, dimethoate, metalkamate, methyl parathion, MIPC, propoxur, and triazophos. Nymphs were removed daily and counted. At 14 days after oviposition, the plants were dissected and the unhatched eggs counted. Carbofuran, triazophos, and methyl parathion reduced egg hatches significantly. No eggs hatched in the carbofuran treatment. Egg hatch

was 37% in the triazophos treatment and 61% in methyl parathion. Further studies indicated that insecticide concentration and age of egg at time of application influenced ovicidal activity (see figure). Five-day-old eggs were more susceptible than 1- and 3-day-old eggs. Concentrations of 0.04 and 0.02% had ovicidal activity on 1-day-old eggs, but concentrations of

0.01 and 0.005% had none.

Another study indicated that granular carbofuran, metalkamate, triazophos, and diazinon at 1 kg a.i./ha in paddy water applied to potted plants containing 1-day-old eggs had ovicidal activity. Carbofuran, metalkamate, and triazophos caused 100% egg mortality. **W**

Base vs canopy insecticide spray for brown planthopper control

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Foliar spray is the most common method of applying insecticide for the control of the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* in the tropics. Because the BPH feeds at the base of the plant, Philippine control recommendations specify that the spray be directed toward the base of the plant—a time-consuming and laborious application method for spraying large areas.

Sprays directed to the base and to the canopy of the plant were compared in three IRRI experiments in 1977. In the first 2 experiments, Perthane was 10 to 20% more effective as a base spray than as a canopy spray. In a third experiment, the two methods were compared using metalkamate, monocrotophos, and Perthane. Perthane sprayed at the base of plants controlled BPH significantly better than when sprayed above the canopy (95 vs 63% control) (see table).

Foliar application of insecticides applied above and below the rice canopy for brown planthopper (BPH) control. IRRI, 1977.

Insecticide ^a	BPH (no./4linear-m row) ^b sampled with D-Vac suction machine		
	Before insecticide application (no.)	2 days after application (no.)	Control ^c (%)
<i>Applied above the rice canopy</i>			
Metalkamate	4,766 a	1,183 a	74
Monocrotophos	8,213 a	3,168 b	60
Perthane	7,342 a	2,589 b	63
No insecticide	6,190 a	5,893 b	5
<i>Applied below the rice canopy</i>			
Metalkamate	11,241 a	947 a	92
Monocrotophos	6,723 a	2,074 b	69
Perthane	7,521 a	335 a	96
No insecticide	7,805 a	8,811 c	0

^aHopper development was induced by foliar application of 30 g a.i. decamethrin/ha starting at 15 days after transplanting. Three applications were made at 750 g a.i./ha. The volume of spray material for both methods was 1,444 liters/ha.

^bIn each column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^cValues shown were adjusted using Abbott's formula.

Metalkamate and monocrotophos sprayed at the base controlled BPH slightly—but not significantly—better than when sprayed above the canopy.

In other 1977 IRRI studies, monocrotophos sprayed only on the leaves controlled BPH feeding on the leaf

sheaths at the base of the plant. That indicates that some insecticides move downward from the upper leaf area to the leaf sheath. The desirability of spraying below the canopy may depend on the insecticide applied. **W**

Contact toxicity of insecticides to the three biotypes of brown planthopper

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In recent years the population of biotype 2 of the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* has increased in farmers' fields in Indonesia and the Philippines. Biotype 2 destroys IR26, which carries the *Bph 1* gene for resistance. In IRRI greenhouse

experiments another biotype, biotype 3, emerged when BPH were forced to feed on such varieties as IR32 that carry the *bph 2* gene for resistance derived from ASD 7. So far biotype 3 has not become abundant in farmers' fields. It is important to know whether a change in biotype predominance in the natural population will also result in a change in susceptibility to the various insecticides.

Previous studies indicated that of the three biotypes, biotype 1 was generally most susceptible to various insecticides

when feeding on rice plants in paddy water treated with granular formulations. In this study the contact toxicity of insecticides to the three biotypes was determined. The insecticides were applied as sprays to the insects using Potter's spray tower.

Results indicated that biotype 1 was least susceptible to the commonly used insecticides carbofuran, metalkamate, diazinon, and methyl parathion (see table). There was no significant difference among biotypes in the decamethrin and

acephate treatments. The differences in results from the cited paddy-water study and from the contact toxicity study reported here may be due to different modes of action of the insecticide in the two application methods. Insecticides applied in the paddy water may have acted primarily as a stomach poison, but the insecticides in this study acted as contact poisons, entering through the cuticle rather than the mouthparts. At any rate, knowing that BPH biotypes differ in their susceptibility to insecticides is important and should be considered when developing strategies for BPH control. *W*

Contact toxicity of insecticides applied with Potter's spray tower at 0.04% concentration against three brown planthopper biotypes. IIRI greenhouse, 1977.

Insecticide	Formulation	Mortality ^a (%)		
		Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3
Decamethrin	2.5 EC	93 a	97 a	90 a
Carbofuran	2 F	68 b	98 a	97 a
Metalkamate	30 EC	64 b	99 a	97 a
Acephate	75 SP	37 a	47 a	37 a
Diazinon	20 EC	24 b	49 a	43 a
Methyl parathion	50 EC	11 b	47 a	35 a
Control		6 a	6 a	4 a

^aMortality reading taken 48 hours after treatment. Average of 4 replications, each consisting of 25 adult insects. Any means for each biotype followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Resistance of brown planthopper to various insecticides at IIRI

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In 1977 carbofuran failed to control the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* at IIRI. Studies using Potter's spray tower and paddy water broadcast methods of application indicated that the strain of BPH that had been exposed to carbofuran for several years (field strain) was resistant (see article, this issue). Further studies using the microapplicator were conducted to compare the field strain's level of resistance to carbofuran and to other insecticides with that of a greenhouse strain that had not been exposed to insecticides.

Both sexes of the field strain had seven times more resistance to carbofuran than the greenhouse strain (see table). The field strain had two to five times

The LD₅₀ value of insecticides applied topically to greenhouse and field strains^a of female and male brown planthoppers. IIRI laboratory, 1977.

Insecticide	Female		ERR ^b	Male		ERR ^b
	LD ₅₀ (µg/g)			LD ₅₀ (dg)		
	Greenhouse strain	Field strain		Greenhouse strain	Field strain	
Carbofuran	0.14	1.05	7.50	0.25	1.78	7.12
Monocrotophos	0.65	3.50	5.38	0.49	2.00	4.08
Metalkamate	1.46	5.37	3.67	2.00	8.68	4.34
Methyl parathion	7.67	23.19	3.02	10.52	13.90	1.32
BPMC	1.95	5.29	2.71	2.89	11.80	4.08
MIPC	1.42	3.29	2.30	5.23	5.59	1.06
Endosulfan	3.09	5.94	1.92	5.12	12.46	2.43
Acephate	2.93	4.96	1.69	3.56	7.79	2.18
N 3727	28.90	32.43	1.12	41.46	43.41	1.04
Perthane	5.13	5.70	1.11	4.45	10.46	2.35
A47171	4.07	4.07	1.00	6.66	5.81	0.87

^aThe greenhouse strain had not been exposed to insecticide and was reared in the greenhouse for about 30 generations. The field strain was reared in the greenhouse for about 4 generations.

^bEstimated resistance ratio = LD₅₀ of field strain divided by LD₅₀ of greenhouse strain.

more resistance to other insecticides that had been used to varying extents at the IIRI farm. Monocrotophos and MIPC have been most commonly used for about

5 years. There was no resistance to newly developed coded compounds, such as N 3727 and A 47171, that had never been used on the farm. *W*

Heavy brown planthopper reinfestations nullify effectiveness of insecticides

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Insecticidal control has often been insufficiently effective against the brown planthopper (BPH) during massive outbreaks over extensive areas. Rapid

and heavy reinfestations from unaffected BPH populations probably are a significant reason, particularly where the entire affected area cannot be treated effectively, uniformly, and simultaneously, as is common under normal field conditions. This was especially evident in recent insecticide trials in Sekinchan, Malaysia, during a BPH outbreak on the rice variety MR 7 at 20 to 26 days after transplanting.

Two fields of 2 ha each were treated with 2 kg a.i. carbofuran/ha (granular broadcast) and 0.1% a.i. monocrotophos (foliar), respectively. Immediately after treatment, 10 plants spaced over each field were randomly selected; each plant was individually enclosed with cylindrical wire and nylon screen cages. The BPH populations on these plants were determined just before treatment and periodically afterwards. Similar BPH